

**FOOD, HEALTH AND ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH
INFRASTRUCTURES TO TACKLE EMERGING PRIORITIES**

Deliverable 1.1

Management Guidelines

TECHNICAL REFERENCES

Grant Agreement number: 101131588

Project website: <https://fheritale.eu/>

Lead Beneficiary: CIRMMMP

Contractual delivery date: 29/02/2014

Actual delivery date: 15/03/2024

Version: 1

Type and dissemination level: Report

Dissemination level: PU

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Funded by the
European Union

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Summary

The present document gathers all the information needed for a smooth management of the FHERITALE project and it is distributed to the partners as a practical guidance for the whole duration of the project.

With the aim to provide a practical handbook, the guidelines include altogether a set of procedures for internal presentations and reports, the list of the deliverables and of the milestones as well as other important information as, for example, reporting periods and how to acknowledge the project. The Guidelines also define risks and contingency plans, as well as impact indicators.

This document agrees with both the terms and conditions of the Grant Agreement and its Annexes and the CA.

1. Governance and Coordination

Governance

The governance of FHERITALE foresees a Coordination Team, a Strategic Board, composed by the Coordination Team and one representative for each of the participating ESFRI RIs, which receives periodic updates by the WP leaders, which are responsible for the execution of the work plan. The highest governing body of the FHERITALE consortium is the General Assembly (GA).

The composition of the governance bodies is:

Coordination Team:

Antonio Rosato, Lucia Banci, and Francesca Morelli (CIRMMP)

Strategic Board:

Lucia Banci and Francesca Morelli (Coordination Team)

Michel Boer - AnaEE-ERIC

Harald Schwalbe - Instruct-ERIC

Jana Klanova - EIRENE

Nastasia Belc - METROFOOD

WP Leaders

WP1 & WP2 – Antonio Rosato (CIRMMP)

WP3 – Jana Klanova (MU)

WP4 – Lavanya Premvardhan (AnaEE-ERIC)

WP5 – Gabriel Mustatea (IBA)

WP6 – Claudia Zoani (ENEA)

WP7 – Enrico Ravera (CIRMMP)

WP 8 – Harald Schwalbe (INSTRUCT-ERIC)

Coordination

The main tasks of the Coordination Team are:

- Coordination of the planned work as outlined in the Grant Agreement
- Supporting the day-to-day project management
- Organization of General Assembly and Strategic Board meetings, minutes and implementation of decisions of these meetings
- Delivering guidelines and procedures to streamline report preparation
- Monitoring of project progress, including revision of deliverables and milestones
- Communication with the EU, submission of deliverables and reports, amendments managements
- Financial administration and distribution of payments to the beneficiaries
- Keeping project records
- Communication within the consortium
- Risk management

2. Procedures for Reporting

The reporting of deliverables and milestones is to be done in good advance with respect to the due delivery date defined in the Grant Agreement (see also Table 1 and Table 2 of this document) according with the following procedures:

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Deliverables

1. Use the template provided by the Coordination Team
2. The WP leader collects input from the involved partners
3. Deliverable submitted to the Coordinator by the WP leader for approval
4. Deliverable uploaded in the EC Portal Continuous Reporting tool by the Coordinator

Milestones

1. The Lead of the milestone collects input from involved partners
2. A short report, or any other evidence of accomplishment, is submitted to the Coordinator by the Lead.
3. The Milestone achievement is registered in the EC Portal Continuous Reporting tool by the Coordinator

Periodic Reports

The project foresees two Reporting Periods (RPs): **RP1 from M1 to M18** and **RP2 from M19 to M36**. The procedure for the preparation of the technical reports is:

1. Use of the template, in agreement with the template available in the EC Portal Periodic Reporting tool, is provided by the Coordination Team
2. The reporting for each WP is coordinated by each WP Leader, who acquires input from involved partners
3. The WP report is submitted to Coordinator by the WP Leader
4. The report is combined and submitted through the EC Portal Continuous Reporting tool by the Coordinator

Financial reports

Being FHERITALE a lump-sum project, financial reporting will adhere to the specific procedure indicated by the EC¹, whose procedure foresees only a single consolidated statement for the consortium about the accomplishment of the various WPs that were completed during the reporting period.

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/how-to-manage-your-lump-sum-grants_en.pdf

3. Keeping records and relevant documentation

To facilitate the account of the project activities during the project life time, we set up a Google Drive folder. The access to this shared folder is restricted to the project partners.

The folder is arranged so that meeting minutes, contacts, logo and templates and any relevant documentation are/will be available to all beneficiaries. Each WP has its own workspace to be filled with activity records/documents.

4. Project Monitoring

The monitoring of the progress of the project will be facilitated by key performance indicators (KPIs) listed below:

- WP1 and WP2: Number of representatives of related RIs participating to strategy meetings and focused groups
- WP1 and WP2: Social media communication: number of visits, posts, likes and interactions, followers
- WP1 and WP2: Number of distributed printed/downloaded promotional material
- WP1 and WP2: Number of papers published, citation index
- WP3: Number of services included in the service catalogue
- WP4: Number of individuated thematic areas
- WP5: Number of key thematic priorities selected for the thematic cluster
- WP6: Number of identified service gaps
- WP7: Number of services selected for the thematic map
- WP8: Number of RIs committed for long term maintenance of the thematic map of services
- All WPs: Number of meetings/workshops organized

For each KPI the Consortium will define a baseline and/or a target value, as appropriate.

5. Risk management

The Coordination Team is responsible of monitoring and solving any operational problem as well as implementing the necessary risk and contingency measures. The potential risks identified at the beginning of the project and the respective mitigation measures are reported in Table 3.

The risk management will be overseen by the Coordination Team with the support of the Strategic Board. The contingency plan will be discussed and approved at the General Assembly meetings. The risk table will be regularly.

6. Acknowledgement and visibility of EU Funding

According to article 17 of the FHERITALE Grant Agreement, communication and dissemination activities of the Consortium partners related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, etc.) and major results funded by the grant must acknowledge the EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate):

The emblem must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands or text. Apart from the emblem, no other visual identity or logo may be used to highlight the EU support.

Any communication or dissemination activity related to the action must use factually accurate information. Where appropriate, the following disclaimer should be included:

“Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

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7. Visibility of the FHERITALE logo

Internal document, technical report and internal or external presentations is expected to include the logo of the project.

Power Point presentations and deliverables will use the templates made available in the shared folder.

8. Tables

Table 1 - List of Deliverables

Number	Deliverable name	Short description	Work package number	Short name of lead participant	Type	Dissemination level	Delivery date (in months)
D1.1	Management Guidelines	Management Guidelines	WP1	CIRMMP	R	PU	2
D1.2	Data Management Plan	Data Management Plan	WP1	CSIC	DM P	PU	4
D1.3	Data Management Plan revision	Data Management Plan	WP1	CSIC	DM P	PU	18
D1.4	Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication	Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication	WP1	INSTRUCT-ERIC	R	PU	6
D1.5	Report on dissemination and outreach activities	Report on dissemination and outreach activities carried out in the first 18 months of the project and update of dissemination plan	WP1	INSTRUCT-ERIC	R	PU	18
D2.1	Data Management Plan revision	Revision of the DMP	WP2	CSIC	DM P	PU	30
D2.2	Report on dissemination and outreach activities	Report on dissemination and outreach activities carried out in the second 18 months of the project	WP2	INSTRUCT-ERIC	R	PU	36
D3.1	Landscaping procedure guidelines	Landscaping procedure guidelines	WP3	MU	R	PU	4

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D3.2	Cross-thematic landscape	Report on services available	WP3	UU	R	PU	18
D4.1	White paper	Public document on the key selected priorities	WP4	AnaEE-ERIC	R	PU	15
D5.1	Categorization of services and technologies	Report on the categorization of existing services and technologies with details on the procedure for analysis of the adaptability of the services to the TRL	WP5	IBA	R	PU	16
D5.2	Strategic technology and service needs	Review and inventory of technology needs related to the key scientific challenges and policy priorities	WP5	SCIENSANO	R	PU	27
D6.1	Gap analysis and technology needs	Report describing main emerging needs, prioritized according to importance/emergency and feasibility	WP6	ENEA	R	PU	22
D6.2	Thematic Cluster definition	Report on the definition of thematic clusters of RIs & services categorized according to technologies, disciplines, and the “One Health”	WP6	IBA	R	PU	30
D7.1	Roadmap for strategic technology development	Report on strategic solutions for the sustainability of the cluster and for the development needed to fill technology gaps	WP7	CIRMMP	R	PU	36
D7.2	Plan for concerted provision of services	Plan for concerted provision of services	WP7	CSIC	R	PU	33
D8.1	Thematic map available	A comprehensive map of services currently accessible publicly available to users	WP8	CIRMMP	DEC	PU	34
D8.2	White paper	Document reporting the FHERITALE coordinated implementation strategy	WP8	INSTRUCT-ERIC	R	PU	36

Table 2 - List of Milestones

Milestone number	Milestone name	Related work package(s)	Due date (in month)	Lead Beneficiary	Means of verification
MS1.1	Project Kick-off	WP1	2	CIRMMP	Meeting organized
MS2.1	FHERITALE Information Campaign	WP2	34	INSTRUCT-ERIC	Informative material published
MS3.1	First catalogue providing valuable insights into the current state of research infrastructures and services	WP3	12	UU	Catalogue published
MS4.1	Summary of thematic priorities	WP4	8	AnaEE-ERIC	Document shared with the consortium members
MS4.2	Strategic retreat meeting	WP4	10	MU	Meeting organised
MS5.1	1 st draft of technologies/services currently used for research focusing on the key thematic priorities	WP5	14	SCIENSANO	Document shared with the consortium members and made available to WP6
MS5.2	List of technology needs and their technology readiness	WP5	18	SCIENSANO	Document shared with the consortium members and made available to WP6
MS6.1	Gap analysis procedures defined	WP6	16	ENEA	Procedures defined and distributed to the consortium
MS6.2	“Map & Thematic cluster” focus group and Map of actors and approaches validated	WP6	22	IBA	Workshop organized, map discussed and validated
MS7.1	Missing services	WP7	24	CIRMMP	Document shared with the consortium members

Table 3 - Risks and mitigation measures

Description of risk (indicate level of (i) likelihood, and (ii) severity: Low/Medium/High)	Work package(s) involved	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
Failure in effective management of the consortium (Low likelihood, high severity)	All WPs	Both the coordinator, and the partners have extensive experience in managing EU projects. Simple management structure with regular, standardized reporting. Provision of Management Guidelines
Failure to engage a critical mass of appropriate stakeholders (Low likelihood, high severity)	All WPs	The consortium has already identified specific stakeholder groups. Review of stakeholder lists.
Delay in recruiting/assigning suitably qualified personnel for the assigned effort (Low likelihood, medium severity)	All WPs	Monitoring of recruitments/tasks assignments by the project manager
Failure of a beneficiary to complete an assigned task (Low likelihood, medium severity)	All WPs	Following decision of the General Assembly, redistribution of tasks and needed resources and formalization of amendment if necessary
Reliance on other Work Packages for content (Medium likelihood, high severity)	WP5, WP6, WP7, WP8	There is a high degree of WP interdependence in FHERITALE. Progresses will be monitored via 1) milestones 2) Strategic Board Meetings 3) topic-focused working groups
Impossibility to run meetings, workshops and events in presence due to sanitary restrictions or other crisis (Medium likelihood, low severity)	WP1, WP2, WP4, WP6, WP8	Work from remotely. Meetings and events moved from in presence to online.